

About the Cover

What will the future bring for three-year-old Dolly? The youngest of four children, she lives with her family in Welfareville in Mandaluyong City, Metro Manila. Dolly's father works in a paint factory. But his pay is "barely enough to make ends meet," says her mother, Susan Umawas, who plans to work abroad someday so she can better provide for her children.

About IRRI

The International Rice Research Institute was established in 1960 by the Ford and Rockefeller Foundations with the help and approval of the Government of the Philippines. Today IRRI is one of 16 nonprofit international research centers supported by the Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research (CGIAR). The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), International Bank for Reconstruction and Development (World Bank), United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), and United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) sponsor the CGIAR. Its membership comprises donor countries, international and regional organizations, and private foundations.

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IRRI 1998-1999

IRRI 1998-1999 RICE: HUNGER OR HOPE?

IRRI

■ IRRI 1998-1999

RICE: HUNGER OR HOPE?

“If we fail to keep agriculture moving in the less-developed nations, poverty will continue to grow, and the social upheaval that will ensue will become a global nightmare.”

Norman Borlaug
1970 Nobel Peace Prize Laureate

“ After decades of work and billions of dollars, chronic hunger is still a major problem in the world. The underlying issues of food security—which include the ability to grow, harvest, process, and store rice and other foods—must be addressed now...But it takes the right mixture of people and resources: the full support of high-level leaders, the dedicated hard work of farmers and extension workers, and access to improved rice varieties. The developed world must summon the political and social will to address the root causes of food shortages.”

Jimmy Carter
Former President, United States

IRRI's Mission

C. Dedolph

Our Goal

To improve the well-being of present and future generations of rice farmers and consumers, particularly those with low incomes

Our Objectives

To generate and disseminate rice-related knowledge and technology of short- and long-term environmental, social, and economic benefit and to help enhance national rice research systems

Our Strategy

We pursue our goal and objectives through

- Interdisciplinary ecosystem-based programs in major rice environments
- Scientific strength from discipline-based divisions
- Anticipatory research initiatives exploring new scientific opportunities
- Conservation and responsible use of natural resources
- Sharing of germplasm, technologies, and knowledge
- Participation of women in research and development
- Partnership with farming communities, research institutions, and other organizations that share our goal

Our Values

Our actions are guided by a commitment to

- Excellence
- Scientific integrity and accountability
- Innovation and creativity
- Diversity of opinion and approach
- Teamwork and partnership
- Service to clients
- Cultural diversity
- Gender consciousness
- Indigenous knowledge
- Environmental protection

IRRI 1998-1999

RICE: HUNGER OR HOPE?

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Abolishing Poverty in Asia

With Asia's stomach growling once again, rice is providing hope for dealing with the intertwined issues of poverty, hunger, soaring population, and environmental degradation.

Every day, 250,000 people join us on our already crowded globe. Most of these people are born into poverty and live their entire lives in poverty, with only death allowing them to escape.

According to the World Bank, 840 million people are going hungry today, two billion are malnourished, and 1.3 billion live in absolute poverty, existing on less than one dollar a day. For many, their lives are driven by a simple obsession: finding their next meal.

What most of us do not realize is that 70 percent of these poor, hungry people live in Asia. South Asia alone is home to half the developing world's poor. Together, Bangladesh and eastern India have as many poor as all of sub-Saharan Africa.

While poverty and hunger in Ethiopia and Somalia have permanently scarred the world's conscience, the longstanding suffering, hunger, and hopelessness of Asia's 800 million desperately poor people are somehow routinely overlooked. Forgotten.

Why?

These victims are living testimonials to our failures: distorted priority setting, social irresponsibility, and lack of global thinking. To still have hunger in our world of abundance is not only unacceptable, it is unforgivable.

In Asia, where nearly all the world's rice is grown and eaten, food means rice. Feeding the poor and helping them work their way out of poverty means starting with the basics: increasing rice production and improving access to rice.

In Asia, plentiful, affordable rice has been the key to maintaining social stability, promoting economic growth, and reducing poverty. As Asia becomes increasingly urban during the next quarter century, growing enough rice for the urban

poor—and finding the land, water, and people to do this—will most likely become hot political issues.

We must ask ourselves two difficult questions: Can the world grow enough rice to feed Asia? And, do we have the means and determination to get this food to the people who need it and ensure that they have access to it?

The fear of famine and penury in Asia in the 1950s propelled concerned people to create the International Rice Research Institute in 1960. The driving force was simple: making the biggest pile of rice possible, as quickly as possible, to feed the ever-multiplying number of hungry mouths. This massive effort gave the world something it desperately needed: time. Time to build national rice research institutions, curb population growth, build more schools, and establish good health programs.

But have we used this time wisely to invest in a healthy world?

IRRI and its partners are once again faced with the daunting challenge of producing more rice, but in a much more complicated and fragile world. With success in keeping Asia fed has come a complacency that is difficult to shake.

The world simply assumes that Asia's growling stomach can be quieted once again: Asian farmers can bring more land into cultivation, irrigate more fields, throw on more fertilizer, plant another crop, and, if more food is needed, it can be grown elsewhere and traded in the global economy. But the quick fixes for boosting production are long gone. In Asia, there is no more new land. Water is becoming scarce. Besides, who wants to be a poor rice farmer when the city at least offers hope for a better life for the next generation? And unlike maize and wheat, little of the rice crop (only 6.6 percent) is traded globally.

R. Cabrera

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“In the last century, some highly motivated people, driven by moral outrage, decided that slavery was monstrous, unconscionable, and must be abolished. They were called abolitionists. Today, widespread hunger in a world of plenty calls equally for moral outrage. The silent holocaust that causes some 40,000 hunger-related deaths every day is unconscionable and must be abolished. We must become the new abolitionists.”

Ismail Serageldin
Chairman, Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research

Each year, 50 million new people—mostly rice eaters—are added to Asia. To feed them, the world must increase its rice output between now and 2020 by one-third more than what is grown and eaten today. Unlike other industries, agriculture cannot simply build more “rice factories” and step up production.

Never before has agriculture faced such a stern challenge. Feeding Asia and providing opportunities for people to free themselves from the shackles of poverty are not impossible. This task requires political will, commitment, and sheer determination among many diverse partners. Agriculture—rice—must be the cornerstone of dealing with the inseparable issues of poverty, hunger, population growth, and environmental degradation.

“Humanity’s greatest challenge may soon be just making it to the next harvest,” Lester Brown of the World Watch Institute warned in 1995. But even if the world can produce enough, getting the food to those who need it is a huge challenge. As Nobel laureate Amartya Sen asserts, “An efficient food distribution system is as important as food self-sufficiency.”

We can keep Asia—and the world—fed if we can correctly set our priorities. We can grow enough food and generate productive employment for the landless so they can buy their food from the market, while maintaining our natural resource base and preserving biodiversity. We can control population growth. We can provide every child with the right to be free from hunger, to be healthy, to go to school, and to eventually earn a decent living—and hope for a better tomorrow.

Human beings must have hope to survive. If people in food-deficit countries see no prospect for ever being free from poverty, they cannot help but lose all hope. And with hopelessness, society unravels.

Hunger or hope?

Our actions today will decide whether Asia’s tomorrow is filled with famine or food security, poverty or prosperity. Asia—and the world—cannot afford for IRRI and its partners to fail. The stakes are simply too high. ■

Ronald P. Cantrell

Ronald P. Cantrell
Director General

R. Kendrick

C. Dedolph

“When scientists and the best of science are devoted to the problems of those who have less in life, that is equity and ethics at its best. For the millions of Asians for whom rice is life, science best serves its human purpose.”

Gelia Castillo
Emeritus Professor of Rural Sociology
University of the Philippines

“Combating hunger should be the topmost priority of the world community. As Nobel laureate in economics Amartya Sen says, ‘Famines do not occur in stable democracies. An efficient food distribution system is as important as food self-sufficiency.’ Economic development leading to gainful employment is essential for combating hunger. Every night, 200 million Indians go to bed hungry, yet India exports 2-4 million tons of rice every year. If everyone had the purchasing power to buy sufficient food, there wouldn’t be any surplus.”

Gurdev S. Khush
1997 World Food Prize Laureate

OPINION

Must There Be Poverty?

Muhammad Yunus
Professor and Managing Director
Grameen Bank, Bangladesh

Poverty is not a natural state of humans. Poor people do not create poverty, nor do people enjoy being poor. Poverty is created by institutions, concepts, and policies. We need to go back to the drawing board to redesign these and remove the barriers.

We must accept the position that we can create a poverty-free world.

To do this, we must change our mind-set so that all humans can be equipped to work themselves out of poverty. Providing access to capital is the single most important step in helping to reduce poverty. But even more basic than that, we must address hunger. To be hungry is to be poor. And if people are poor, they are often also hungry or undernourished.

The International Rice Research Institute was not created for the benefit of multinationals. IRRI exists because of hunger.

There must be a strong connection between IRRI and reducing poverty. People must know that IRRI believes in a poverty-free world and has fixed its research agenda around this goal. Only then can IRRI and its partners succeed in helping to change the world’s mind-set and doing what needs to be done.

IRRI does not do research on rice for rice’s sake; it does research to benefit the poor. The world cannot afford to have scientists who only do research. All scientists need to have a picture of a hungry person—and know they are working for that less fortunate person. All scientists need to think about how their research will help to provide extra rice for that person.

High-yielding varieties have lowered rice prices and helped to create the feeling that there’s enough rice. Alleviating the fear of famine has truly been one of IRRI’s major successes. But this puts the responsibility on IRRI to give the signal when it sees things are not working out. ■

C. Decoliph

“Poor people in Asia can live without grapes to make wine, but they cannot live without rice.”

The Facts of Rice

Population, Poverty, and Food Security in Asia

Poverty amid plenty, shrinking birthrates and swelling population, more rice and more hunger: Asia's future will be filled with contradictions. Can the continent cope?

In much of Asia, plentiful, cheap rice has been the propelling force behind economic, political, and social stability. Rice has kept the continent nourished, employed, and peaceful.

"The true 'Asian miracle' hasn't been stunning economic development," says IRRI economist Mahabub Hossain. "It's been keeping people fed."

And food in Asia means rice.

This vast continent grows—and eats—more than 90 percent of all the world's rice on more than 250 million tiny farms, with most Asians eating rice two or three times a day. Half of every harvest never even leaves the farm: it feeds the family that planted it. Hundreds of millions of poor people spend half to three-fourths of their incomes on rice—and nothing else. For these people, rice anchors their precarious lives.

Farmers have grown an astounding 2.5 percent more rice each year since 1965. This "extra rice" feeds an additional 600 million people, and has stayed neck and neck with the ever-growing demand. Increasingly bountiful rice harvests from the late 1970s through the late 1980s—mainly thanks to high-yielding modern varieties, more irrigation, and more access to credit—have accounted for nearly four-fifths of this growth. The result? A stunning drop in the real price of rice.

Dr. Hossain describes this cheap rice as "the single most important contribution" IRRI has made in Asia. This rice has helped to reduce poverty by enabling the rural landless and the urban working class to buy more food with the same income.

But rice alone cannot change the world, with recent World Bank figures telling the story: 1.3 billion people still live in poverty, 840 million suffer from hunger, and 2 billion are malnourished. Seventy percent of these people are Asians, and half the developing world's poor live in South Asia. Al-

though many countries experienced success in reducing poverty through rapid economic growth, the financial crisis that began in mid-1997 is causing some to slide backward.

Another billion hungry rice eaters will be added in Asia by 2020. Then, more than four billion people—more than half the world's population—will depend on rice. Will Asia be able to grow enough rice? And will it be able to get this food to everyone who needs it? A hard look at the situation provides a cold-shower dose of reality—and hope that Asia can cope.

Drowning in People

While growing prosperity and the urbanization of Asia factor into the equation, the demand for rice boils down to one thing: population. Most Asian countries are still growing at an astounding 1.5 to 2.8 percent per year. (The exceptions are China, Japan, Republic of Korea, and Thailand.) Despite the United Nations' encouraging estimates that population growth rates for the next 25 years will be half of what they've been the past 25 years, it's already too late to stop the massive tidal wave of humanity.

The absolute increase in Asia's people over the next 30 years will essentially be as large as over the past 30 years, primarily because of the expanded population base. Asia's humanity is projected to increase from 1995's 3.4 billion to about 4.8 billion in 2025. Ironically, the poorest populations will continue to grow the fastest. In South Asia, population is projected to increase by 732 million between 1995 and 2025—surpassing the 670 million added between 1965 and 1995.

Demand for rice during the next 25 years is expected to increase by 65 percent in the Philippines, 51 percent in Bangladesh, 46 percent in India, 45 percent in Vietnam, and

R. Cabrera

"Countries that have not been able to control human population growth are in serious trouble because of an upward spiraling demand for food. Rice research alone will never be able to keep up with the increase in human population. Rice research and managing human population growth, therefore, go hand in hand."

Mechai Viravaidya
Chairman
Population and Community Development Association
Thailand

38 percent in Indonesia. In one generation, for example, the Philippines' population will grow from today's 75 million to 115 million. "The Philippines is already importing rice," Dr. Hossain says. "What will it do in 25 years?"

Total demand also depends on the number of rural and urban people, poor and rich. By 2020, half of Asia's population will be urban (see p. 14). Dr. Hossain predicts that urbanization will actually dampen Asia's overall demand for rice. But, with growing affluence, the demand for high-quality rice will surge and that for "ordinary" rice will decline. Poor people,

whether rural or urban, typically eat more rice than rich people. But, with economic growth and reduced poverty, demand for rice is expected to escalate in poverty-stricken regions of Asia as the poor satisfy their unmet food needs.

How Much Will They Eat?

The demand for rice has grown annually at 2.5 percent over the past three decades. Mercifully, during the next quarter century, it is projected to grow at only 1 percent annually according to IRRI's sister institution,

the International Food Policy Research Institute. The main reasons? Slower economic growth since mid-1997 and less demand for rice in East Asia. But, in poverty-ridden countries, demand for rice will explode.

More mouths to feed translates into a need for one-third more "new rice" than what is eaten today. The figures are frightening. Farmers must consistently produce an extra 6.7 million tons of unmilled rice—every year—without fail. Even if this can be achieved, it will merely maintain current nutrition levels, which are already inadequate for hundreds of millions of people.

R. Cabrera

No More Quick Fixes

The magic Green Revolution formula of more productive rice varieties, more fertilizer, and more water for irrigation pushed Asia's rice production off the charts. Between 1966 and 1997, production grew by 116 percent and yield accelerated by 88 percent, while area expanded by only 15 percent. But population zoomed from 1.9 billion to 3.5 billion, and poverty remained endemic.

With so much more food, why then do hunger and poverty still persist in Asia? The closing

of the land frontier and uncontrolled population growth are "undoing the good work of the Green Revolution," says Professor S.R. Osmani of the University of Ulster. "If the entitlement-enhancing effects of modern varieties do not seem to reduce poverty, it's because these effects aren't strong enough to outweigh the impoverishing force unleashed by population growth."

Despite keeping Asia fed, researchers, watchdog groups, and government officials are once again sounding the alarm and trying to shake off the complacency of success. Rice harvests have slackened since the mid-1980s and

have failed to outpace demand in several countries. Dr. Hossain believes this is the beginning of a long-term trend rather than a cyclical downswing. And this could spell trouble for Asia.

With it only taking 11 years now for the world to add another billion people, never before has so much been expected so quickly from agriculture. Tomorrow's farmers will have to grow this extra rice without the quick-fix boosts of the past: new land, abundant water, cheap labor, and high responsiveness to extra fertilizer. And, their rice will have to compete on the cut-throat global market.

C. Daddolph

C. Daddolph

"When you are poor, you are poor: you have no money, no food, no home, no dignity, and, eventually, no hope.... We must liberate ourselves from the oppression of poverty through our own efforts, initiatives, and resourcefulness."

Joseph Estrada
Philippine President
(Who campaigned as "President for the Poor")

C. Dedolph

“Despite the Green Revolution, millions in Asia remain poor and are effectively excluded from any benefits of globalization. Improving their lives will require, among others, a new doubly green revolution that begins with the needs of the poor, identifies research priorities appropriate to those needs, and seeks innovative solutions that address those needs.”

Gordon Conway
President, The Rockefeller Foundation

Public-sector rice research is crucial to avoiding possible increases in real prices during the coming 20 years. Without this research, improved seed varieties and other new technologies will not be available to peasant rice growers of the world."

Kenzo Hemmi, Professor
Toyo Eiwa Women's University, Japan

Where Have All the Rice Fields Gone?

Rice farmers are already having difficulties coaxing more rice from their fields. But in the future they will have even less land for growing rice as factories, roads, houses, skyscrapers, and parking lots devour fields. In Java alone, 30,000 hectares of agricultural land vanish each year—which could supply rice for 800,000 people. Rice will also have to compete with more lucrative crops for field space.

Water Fights

Although the amount of water on Earth doesn't change, its availability for rice farming will become only a trickle of what it once was. The battle for water is becoming fierce as population balloons and economic development intensifies. Governments will most likely continue to divert water from agriculture to give priority to water for drinking, sanitation, and industry. Few options are left for economically expanding irrigation in profitable and environment-friendly ways.

Who Wants to Be a Rice Farmer?

Simple economics dictates that when people see an opportunity to earn more, they move—especially from low-paying, back-breaking, seasonal agricultural work. And who can blame them? Today, the rural landscape is increasingly populated by old people, children, and women—the men and the young have migrated to the cities.

Asia will increasingly be challenged by how to make rice farming attractive for the next generation. "I don't want my four children to be farmers," says Thai rice farmer Wan Dapan. "I want them to be involved in business—a farmer's life is too difficult."

Fertilizer Woes

Fertilizer fatigue is an ailment that rice and other crops increasingly experience: adding the same amount of fertilizer—or more—doesn't give as much grain as it used to for many farmers.

"We're worried about just maintaining current rice production levels, let alone increasing them," says Dr. Osamu Ito, head of IRRI's Agronomy, Plant Physiology, and Agroecology Division. Fertilizer-use efficiency must be boosted in environment-friendly ways. Varieties that are more responsive to fertilizer—whether organic or manufactured—require rice researchers to go all out using both conventional plant breeding and biotechnology.

Global Trade Dampens Rice Production

Unlike any other major commodity, only 6.6 percent of all the world's rice is traded on the international market. The rest is eaten in the country where it was grown, making the prospects for alleviating rice deficits through imports a bit complex.

Exporting surplus rice just doesn't pay for middle- and high-income countries, which generally grow only enough rice to feed themselves. In the late 1980s, the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) reported that it cost about 17 times more to grow rice in Japan than in Thailand and Vietnam, and about 10 times more than in Australia and the United States.

High-cost domestic production on small family farms prohibits richer Asian countries from competing with poorer Asian countries, where wages are low and family labor is still available, and with agricultural giants, such as Australia and the United States, which reap economies of scale on large farms.

When the Uruguay Round of the General Agreement on Tariffs and Trade is fully implemented, beware: the years of protecting domestic rice industries will haunt high-cost producers. When domestic markets are opened, cheap imported rice will flood the market, driving down

R. Cabrera

C. Dedolph

Bangladesh's Tenuous Triumph

In a country so hungry that poor people steal rice from rat holes, food insecurity is a serious threat.

Rice research has been directly responsible for Bangladesh's ability to feed itself.

Flood, drought, politics, and the resettlement of 10 million civil war refugees ignited the great famine of 1974, which caused massive human misery and starvation. The flood of 1998 was equally destructive, with the Bangladesh government reporting a loss of 2 million tons of rice worth \$630 million.

But no famine followed the flood of 1998, thanks to political will and increased rice production—a direct result of research. One of the most important factors helping the country get through this crisis is the high-yielding irrigated dry-season (*boro*) crop. Boro rice has reduced the country's dependence on its 40 percent deeply flooded land, which yields no rice in years of disastrous floods. With the innovations of groundwater tube wells for irrigation and modern high-yielding and shorter-duration boro rice varieties, farmers have been abandoning the risky low-yielding deepwater rice in favor of boro rice. This crop expanded from 0.9 million hectares in 1970 to 3.0 million in 1997.

Boro rice has made life better for many rural Bangladeshis. Muhammed Nizamuddin has been planting his 1-hectare farm in Manikganj District to modern boro varieties for years. "Boro rice costs more to grow, but there's more food," says the farmer, who no longer has to buy rice to feed his family. Paresh Chandra Sarkar, a 50-year-old agricultural laborer, also says he is doing better with boro rice. "Now there's more work."

The world's most densely populated country, Bangladesh supports 128 million people. The average density is 900 persons per square kilometer. Despite a declining population growth rate (from 3 percent annually in 1965 to 1.7

percent today), the nation is still adding 2.2 million people each year. Per capita income is extremely low (\$230 in 1994), with people spending nearly two-thirds of their income on food—35 percent on rice alone—and even more for the desperately poor.

Rice production has grown at an amazing 2.5 percent per year over 1976-94 on the same amount of cropped land (10 million hectares). This increase is almost exclusively because of the higher yields of modern varieties, which are

grown on 60 percent of the land. This rice amounted to 9 million extra tons in 1993—enough to feed 40 million people.

Benefits from technological progress—modern varieties, irrigation, and the like—are estimated to be \$300 million per year, 17 times more than the country's *total* investment in rice research and technology transfer. With more efficient production has come a slight decline in rural poverty, and a drop in the rice price of 1.6 percent per year.

The future is tenuous, however, with Bangladeshi farmers needing to grow 2.5 percent more cereals each year if the country is to avoid additional imports. But there is no more land for expanding production, with nearly two-thirds of the nation's total land mass of 14 million hectares already used to grow food—three-fourths of this area for rice alone.

Without technological progress, IIRI economist Mahabub Hossain estimates that rice production could never have outpaced population and would have grown at most by 1 percent per year. Unless supplemented by additional grain imports, the price would have increased, worsening food insecurity and poverty.

"If Bangladesh is to continue feeding its population and to increase its ability to cope with natural disaster, technological progress must continue in the future." Dr. Hossain says. ■

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Asia Goes Urban

Asia is a continent on the move—and its future will be a crowded one: by 2020 half its population will be urban. Is mass rural-urban migration good for the region?

Going urban brings good things to life. Just ask the hundreds of millions of Asians who have made the journey from the countryside to the city. Despite the pollution and slums, most say they're better off.

Asia is urban—and increasingly so, thanks to recent economic prosperity and industrial growth. Whether it's hope for work and a better life, endemic poverty, natural disaster, or politics, migration has been the main reason for the swelling of the cities. But too many people crowding into too little space can spell environmental and social disaster.

Today, the continent is home to nine of the world's 14 megacities of more than 10 million people. And experts at the Asian Development Bank predict even more monster cities on the horizon: by 2015 Asia will have 17 of the world's 27 megacities.

Urban Bloat

In 1965, Asia had a rural population of 1.5 billion and an urban population of 430 million. But today about one-third (1.2 billion) of the population is urban. By 2025, the rural population will not have changed from today's 2.3 billion, but the urban population will have soared to 2.5 billion—about half of Asia's total.

"Urbanization is an inevitable element of the development process," says IRRI economist Mahabub Hossain. And in his opinion, rural to urban migration cannot be controlled as long as there are economic incentives for people to move.

But a few monster cities aren't desirable either, emphasizes the economist. Dhaka, for example, is a potential disaster in the making. In 1990, it was the 28th largest city in the world, with a population of 6.2 million and density of 5,050 persons per square kilometer. In 2015, it is projected to be the fifth largest—and home to 19.5 million.

"We don't want to see Dhaka become a megacity—a mega nightmare," says Muhammad Yunus of the Grameen

Bank. The key to preventing this, he believes, is to figure out why some people don't leave the farms and small cities, and learn from them about how to make life outside megacities more attractive. "There's no reason why one city should suck the entire country into it," says Professor Yunus.

But what if everyone stayed put in the countryside?

"Then the situation of the poor would be much worse," says Dr. Rita Afsar, research fellow at the Bangladesh Institute of Development Studies and IRRI collaborator. "Migration is typically adapted as a strategy for self-help."

ADB photo

Good for Rural Asia

Despite all the social and environmental headaches it brings, urbanization has actually been good for rural Asia: landholdings have gotten bigger and labor shortages have forced farmers to mechanize, both of which contribute to increased efficiency in agriculture. Rural-urban migration has also eased the pressure on land in rural areas. In some places, urban slum dwellers are much better off than the rural landless and marginal landowners.

Going urban requires a lot of planning for a smooth transition. Dr. Hossain says that some absolute musts involve decentralizing government to the local level and improving infrastructure, such as housing, communication systems, roads, electricity, water and sanitation, and education and health systems—and providing more access to capital and food.

Feeding the Cities

One of the bonuses of urbanization is that rice demand per person should go down. Dr. Hossain and his colleagues have documented that, at the same income level, city people in Bangladesh and Thailand eat less rice than their rural relatives, primarily because city workers have less physically taxing work.

But with 50 million new rice consumers—or five new Calcuttas—added each year, Asia still faces an uphill battle to feed these extra mouths, most of whom will be poor. Meet-

ing this challenge will require switching from a “subsistence to commercial mentality,” says Dr. Hossain. A smaller, more efficient rural population can support huge urban populations if the proper economic incentives exist and new technologies are widely adopted.

The fragile flood-prone areas and the uplands will remain subsistence rice production areas and cannot be expected to help feed the cities. The greatest potential for increasing rice production lies in the rainfed lowlands, which may be able to contribute some extra rice to the cities. But production in these monsoon-dependent areas remains low. In eastern India, for example, yields are only about 2 tons per hectare compared with more than 5 tons in Punjab and Tamil Nadu, where all the rice land is irrigated. New technologies may help to boost production, but the outcome is uncertain.

Keeping urban consumers fed will boil down to continued reliance on Asia’s traditional rice bowls: the highly productive, intensive irrigated rice-based systems. But these fields are already about as bountiful as they can be considering the rice plant’s genetics and current technologies and input levels.

New technologies are needed to increase land productivity and input-use efficiency. Two of the most promising are a new plant type, which will have a yield advantage of about 20 percent over today’s best varieties, and tropical hybrid rice, with a yield advantage of 15 percent over current varieties (see p. 32).

“Increased production from irrigated fields is an absolute must if rice prices are to remain affordable to the poor,” says Gurdev Khush, IRRF’s principal plant breeder. ■

“Cities and people are like sugar and ants. We shouldn’t put all the sugar in the cities, because all the ants will go there. We need to sprinkle more sugar in other places.”

Made Oka
Economist, Center for Agro-Socioeconomic
Research, Indonesia

Maintaining low rice prices through technological innovation is critical to stabilizing the extremely precarious lives of people like Mr. Kholita and his family.

Booming and Busting in Bangkok

Widow Ron Konthongkam and her six grown-up children left their small rice farm in northern Thailand four years ago for one reason: pursuit of a better life. Klong Toey, Bangkok's largest slum, became their new home.

But it is not exactly what one would call home sweet home.

For the first few years, slum life was tolerable. The children all had jobs, and they had money enough to get by. But since mid-1997 and the economic turmoil, the family has once again plunged into hardship and misery reminiscent of the farming days.

The children have all lost their jobs, with her youngest daughter Banchonrak clinging to her food server position the longest, but she was recently let go too.

Exhausted, worried—but not hopeless. Her face reveals troubles—and those of thousands of her neighbors—as she talks about her life's struggle. At 72 years old, Ms. Ron depends on her children for her daily rice. But they have no incomes.

The tough old woman says she will stay put in Klong Toey, and her children will keep looking for work. Returning to her past in Petchaboon, where she buried her husband and six other children, is out of the question: "I won't go back there."

Making Ends Meet in Manila

Her address sounds as depressing as the place: Block 38, Welfareville, Mandaluyong City, Metro Manila. A former government welfare area for orphans, Welfareville is now one of the sprawling city's biggest slums.

It is home to drug dealers, prostitutes, and 46-year-old Bida Obeda, her alcoholic husband, and their 13 children who range in age from 2 to 26. She used to have a relatively profitable food

business, and her husband used to own a silkscreen printing business. Both went bankrupt a few years ago, forcing the family to move in with a brother-in-law. The industrious woman now earns money by taking in laundry, selling bread, and cooking food to sell to neighbors.

"We are used to the ups and downs of life," says Ms. Obeda. "One day you have everything, and the next you have nothing."

Although the impact of the financial crisis on the Philippines has not been as dramatic as in neighboring countries, the Obeda family feels the pain. They used to eat 6 kilograms of rice a day, but now they make do with 4. And when there's not enough money to buy 4 kilograms, the solution is simple: skip a meal, or the children who attend school don't eat lunch.

Nine of the children are still at home, and all of them go to school—when there's money. "My dream is to see every one of my children finish school, but..." her voice trails off.

Still, life in a slum is better than in the province. "I have no plan to go back home—there is nothing left for me there," she says. "I was a self-supporting student when I came to Manila 30 years ago, and I will remain that way." ■

C. Dedolph

G. Hettel

(L-R) Ron Konthongkam in Bangkok, Bida Obeda in Manila, Kholita and Amena in Dhaka, Ratmah and her children in Jakarta

Indonesia provides a sobering lesson about what could happen in the absence of any government intervention. The stunning plunge of the Indonesian rupiah during the financial crisis—from Rp 2,500 to 15,000 to the dollar—would have triggered a sixfold increase in the domestic rice price within a few months, while consumer incomes remained stagnant. Rice prices did increase substantially, but, thanks to the government's stabilization policies, the increase was much less than a factor of six and was not abrupt. Without these policies, widespread famine might have occurred.

In the name of stability, however, many governments have intervened excessively in domestic grain marketing, ignoring the crucial role of the private sector. Much research, at IRRRI and elsewhere, has shown that private traders are more efficient at moving farm inputs and outputs.

"The challenge for economists and policymakers is to find cost-effective mechanisms that provide for adequate stability, yet still preserve as many of the benefits of free trade as possible and allow the private sector to have a dominant role," says Dr. Dawe.

All for One

With the increasing costs of labor, land, and water, it will be more efficient for richer countries to shift resources away from growing their own rice and buy their supplies from countries with a comparative advantage in producing rice. "Before the economic crisis in Asia, many political leaders were in favor of adopting this strategy—but no longer," says Dr. Hossain. Because the political costs of failing to feed their people are so incredibly high, most governments are not willing to take this risk.

"Asian nations need to collaborate mutually to strengthen agricultural research and develop irrigation and marketing infrastructure," says Dr. Hossain. International support is required to address food security in places with extensive poverty, that are threatened by political instability, or that have a vulnerable natural resource base. All this requires political will, changes in philosophy, and regional cooperation. What happens to rice in Asia will largely be based on politics—the same as always. ■

"For those of us on the food production front, let us all remember that world peace will not be built on empty stomachs and human misery. Deny the small-scale farmers of the developing world access to modern factors of production, and humankind will be doomed, not from poisoning and environmental melt-down, as some say, but from starvation and social and political chaos."

Norman Borlaug
1970 Nobel Peace Prize
Laureate

From Rice to Riches—And Back to Rice

With the economic crisis melting the tiger economies, rice has reemerged as a powerful force—and as an old friend. Southeast Asia is learning some painful lessons as dramatically different economic and political fates unfold.

For most rural poor in Indonesia, life is much the same as always. Largely untouched by the recent boom years, and largely untouched by the economic crisis, their lives continue to be both impoverished and nourished by rice.

Outside Bojong Jaya village in West Java, the husband-wife team of Sanaim and Aliah works in unison with 25 other laborers, all busy threshing and sacking rice. For every seven 50-kilogram sacks packed, they get to keep one. Their earnings will amount to about 15 sacks, and that's it until the next harvest.

Like many of Indonesia's landless rural poor—some 11 million households on Java alone—they are oblivious to the price of rice: whatever they earn, they eat.

"At least we have rice to feed our family," says Ms. Aliah. If only the hundreds of thousands of jobless families in Jakarta could say the same thing. Their trouble has been double: little money and high rice prices.

Down But Not Out

Miat used to be a security guard at a Jakarta construction site. He was laid off in early 1998, and has been jobless ever since. He, his wife Nenti, and their family, after months of searching for work, found themselves in Bekasi, an eastern suburb of Jakarta.

Their luck suddenly changed for the better when they became part of a self-help "seed and feed" project sponsored by the United Nations Development Programme and administered by

the Indonesian Ministry of Social Affairs. Each of the participating families—a thousand or so—is given rice and vegetable seeds to plant on abandoned suburban land, and enough rice to eat until their first harvest. Then they're on their own for deciding what to do with the produce: eat it, sell it, or replant it.

Mr. Miat says his family is extremely grateful. "The project has helped us to hold on until I can find a job again." And the children, Firman and Miasi, have been able to stay in grade school.

Back to Rice

More than 5 million new entrants—including the Miat family—have moved into the agricultural sector since August 1997, when the financial crisis hit Indonesia. It's not exactly traditional agriculture, nor is it by choice, but peri-urban agriculture is helping many jobless Indonesians cope with economic hardship.

With most jobless persons being too embarrassed to go back home, the suburbs and small cities around Jakarta are becoming socioeconomic buffer zones. With their vast tracts of land—once destined for urban development but now abandoned—these areas are helping the jobless scrape out a living until better times return.

Even if millions did go back to their home

(L-R) Sanaim, Aliah, Nenti and Miat

G. Hettel

G. Hettel

Making Nutritionists Believe

So far, so good, but a major obstacle remains in convincing nutritionists that the iron and zinc in this rice are “bioavailable” for humans—and don’t just “go down the tube,” as Dr. Graham puts it.

The optimistic scientists are putting the high-nutrient rice through rigorous testing to prove beyond a doubt that this extra iron is present after milling and absorbed in humans.

Experiments conducted in collaboration with Dr. Ross Welch and his team at the United States Department of Agriculture-Agricultural Research Service’s Plant, Soil, and Nutrition Laboratory at Cornell University verified that the extra iron and zinc are available to rats and human colon cell cultures (which simulate a human intestine). But the gut of a rat is different from that of a human, and colon cells in a petri dish are not the same as the real thing. And that is why human feeding trials must be done.

In collaboration with researchers at the Institute of Human Nutrition of the University of the Philippines Los Baños, a large-scale trial is under study to begin in mid-1999 at a convent in the Philippines. “It could be the perfect place for a study,” says Dr. Gregorio. “The postulants and novitiates are all young women of about the same age who eat the same amount of the same food every day.”

Next Steps

Although the science is new and risky, researchers are confident they can do more than just increase rice supplies as food. “We’re optimistic that we’re on to something big,” says Dr. Graham. “We are calling for a new paradigm for agriculture: sustainable, productive, nutritious food systems. To achieve our goals, we need a new alliance of agricultural and health professionals researching and defining those systems.”

If they succeed, the lives of the poorest of the poor—especially women and children—can be drastically improved through more nutritious rice. ■

Starving for Nutrition

Sahernaz, who lives in the Agargaon slum in Dhaka, cannot make enough breast milk to satisfy her baby’s hunger. It’s no wonder: she says she eats only one meal of rice a day.

In Bangladesh, two out of every three children are malnourished, shorter and lighter than what they should be, anemic, and unable to ward off diseases. This comes as no surprise in a country where rice supplies 76 percent of all calories, and people are lucky if they eat two meals a day. The result is one generation of weak, malnourished people giving birth to another in a never-ending cycle that is “simply alarming,” says Khurshed Jahan, a nutrition professor at the Institute of Nutrition and Food Science, University of Dhaka.

Cooking habits, polished rice, and the cultural tradition that men eat first—and more and better than the women—combined with poverty make a recipe for pervasive malnutrition. Children and women are hardest hit.

Professor Jahan’s hope?

“Opportunities must be created for rural people—both women and men—to become more active income generators through increased agricultural production and cottage industry,” she stresses. “Women will spend their money on their children. But if they aren’t the ones who earn it, they have no control.” ■

C. Dedolph

Cambodia's Long Journey Back

Crushed by years of civil strife and hunger, Cambodians are rebuilding their nation. Rice research is helping to feed the country, reclaim time, and replant hope.

The 1970s and early '80s were times when normal life ceased in Cambodia, and few had enough to eat. Most farmers stopped growing rice. One and a half million people died.

Today, peace and rice are at the core of Cambodia's recovery. Recent democratic elections and the opening of the economy have renewed hope for a return to normalcy. But many families remain on the edge, impoverished, hungry, and with little hope. For them, the starting point must be rice: 85 percent of the people are rice farmers, and rice provides three-fourths of the daily calories.

"We don't want to beg for rice from other countries," says Lim Kean Hor, Cambodian Secretary of State. "Rice is the best way to improve food security, stimulate economic development, and help poor farmers."

Starting from Ground Zero

The Vietnam War, Cambodia's own civil war, and then Pol Pot's Khmer Rouge regime plunged the country into a time when little rice was harvested. When liberation forces entered Cambodia in 1979, the country's rice-growing capacity had shrunk to only 20 percent of the 3.8 million tons harvested in 1970. Its research and extension infrastructure—both human and physical—was destroyed. The irrigation systems were demolished or dilapidated, and fields were planted with millions of antipersonnel mines instead of rice. The national genebank was gone, and hungry refugees had eaten seed stocks.

Farmers did the best they could, but food insecurity remained a serious problem. In 1986, Cambodia's Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries (MAFF) invited IRRI to help the country restore Cambodia's rice capability. With funding from the Australian Agency for International Development

(AusAID), the Cambodia-IRRI-Australia Project (CIAP) was launched in 1987 with a dual agenda: increase rice production as quickly as possible to improve food security, and develop Cambodia's agricultural research capacity.

"You can't have development without food. In Cambodia, rice is food and central to life," says Bill Costello, First Secretary of AusAID in Cambodia. "That's why Australia is assisting Cambodia through CIAP."

In the Rice Again

Cambodia reached a milestone in 1995: self-sufficiency in rice for the first time in 25 years. Even more amazing, the country also produced a rice surplus of 139,000 tons of milled rice for export. Cambodian farmers have kept these production levels up ever since.

In May 1997, Chann Saphan, the Undersecretary of State for Agriculture, unequivocally attributed Cambodia's return to surplus rice production to research. More farmers planting higher-yielding varieties from IRRI and CIAP, expanded dry-season rice area, improved pest management, and increased distribution and use of fertilizer are the main reasons, says Harry Nesbitt, CIAP team leader and agronomist since 1988.

When both the dry-season and wet-season crops are combined, 1.1 million tons more rice (worth \$126 million) was eaten by Cambodians or sold in 1997 over 1992 amounts. If only 15 percent of this amount were attributed to rice research, the value would be \$18.9 million, which exceeds the total funds invested in CIAP.

Three-fourths of this additional rice is from the wet-season crop, which 80 percent of Cambodian farmers grow. Despite the national surplus, 40 percent of the population is still short of food, illustrating that food security involves more than just increasing rice production.

R. Cabrera

“Lost” Varieties Returned

One of the most dramatic stories about the resurrection of rice research in Cambodia is the return of the “lost” indigenous rice varieties. Many traditional Cambodian rice varieties disappeared during the civil strife because seed reserves were eaten and farmers were discouraged from growing deepwater rice. Fortunately, 765 duplicate samples had been sent to the International Rice Genebank in the Philippines. At the government’s request, IRRI returned the safely conserved seeds.

These “new” traditional varieties are once again growing in Cambodian farmers’ fields—as they have been for centuries. Nineteen of the 34 varieties released since 1990 have been from these restored seeds and more recent in-country collection efforts. The varieties all have the letters “CAR,” which signify Cambodian rice.

Dr. Nesbitt predicts that these high-yielding and good-tasting varieties will spread throughout rainfed areas—if enough good seed is made available to farmers. Seed multiplication is increasingly being done through nongovernment organizations (NGOs) and multilateral aid programs.

Listening to the Farmers

CIAP has been trying to hear the voice of farmers in everything it does. “We try to get ideas from farmers and build on their experiences,” says CIAP agricultural economist Peter Cox. With the majority of Cambodians being subsistence farmers, creating appropriate, low-cost technologies is challenging. “We are cognizant that not all

the technologies being developed are suitable for the poorest of the poor,” says Dr. Nesbitt. “But as they become better off, they will be able to use them.”

“Some farmers say that CIAP technology is too costly,” says Seung Keoviseth, CIAP socioeconomic assistant since 1995. “We try to learn from these people by asking what would be useful and affordable.”

CIAP has been listening to what farmers—and rural landless people—have to say through on-farm experiments, farmer participatory research, integrated pest management (IPM) experiments, and surveys.

The key is flexibility. “Different strategies are needed for different farmers,” explains Mak Solieng, CIAP socioeconomic specialist. “If they are very poor, we try to fit production strategies to their situations.” Innovative, appropriate technologies, some of which are very low-cost, have been the result.

Integrated pest management provides a good example. CIAP entomologists have developed appropriate IPM techniques, shared them with farmers through field schools, and encouraged them to do their own experiments. Pesticide use is still low in Cambodia, so the timing is perfect to implement IPM.

Weeds cause yield losses of 20-30 percent, much of which could be recaptured if farmers level their fields and prepare them better. “Farmers don’t need big equipment to level their fields, they just need water and shovels,” says agricultural engineer Joe Rickman.

Seed quality could be improved through the widespread adoption of simple farmer practices, and massive waste stopped. Mr. Rickman estimates that only 20 percent of all

R. Cabrera

“We don’t want to beg for rice from other countries. Rice is the best way to improve food security, stimulate economic development, and help poor farmers.”

Lim Kean Hor
Secretary of State, Cambodia
(Talking with farmers and extensionists at a CIAP field day)

CIAP Achievements 1989-1999

- Released 34 varieties
- Developed recommendations for efficient fertilizer use
- Created new approach for identifying Cambodian soils
- Developed crop protection strategies using environment-sound integrated pest management practices
- Demonstrated value of land leveling and on-farm water conservation techniques
- Conducted quantitative socioeconomic surveys that have contributed to the understanding of Cambodian rice-farming households
- Introduced a farming systems approach to integrate other crops into the rice farm
- Furthered the professional development of women agricultural scientists and technicians
- Sponsored formal and informal training in-country and abroad
- Developed research infrastructure across 16 provinces

Source: AusAID

seed planted establishes, meaning that 160,000 tons of rice rots in the field—rice that could be eaten.

Building Rice Research Capacity

CIAP's long-term work has been to build infrastructure: physical and human. The permanency of rice research has hinged on the government establishing the Cambodian Agricultural Research Institute (CARDI), which is now coming to life.

A "long and painful process," Dr. Nesbitt says it took nine years to resolve a land ownership dispute before the government could provide 70 hectares for the CARDI field station in 1997.

From these rice fields has risen CARDI: a training center, shed, eight kilometers of roads,

C. Dedolph

and one kilometer of irrigation canals. To celebrate the achievement, a field day was held in October 1998 to inaugurate the training center and to provide an opportunity for more than 500 people—farmers, extensionists, NGO workers, donor representatives, and private agricultural entrepreneurs—to learn more about rice research.

"I'm happy to visit here," said farmer Tol Kim, who owns one hectare of rice land near the station. "I came to learn."

Partnerships in Development

For research to be useful, its results need to get to the people who can use them. CIAP freely shares its information, recommendations, and experiences with NGOs, semigovernment organizations, international organizations, and anyone else who needs rice-related information. A recent partner in getting the information out has been the Department of Agricultural Extension, assisted by the new Cam-

Eight in 6 Billion

A few among the many, these people are just a handful of Asia's poor. Someday, they hope to have the right to be free from hunger, be healthy, go to school, and earn a decent living—and have hope for a better tomorrow.

R. Cabrera

■
Juan Reyes (not his real name) used to be a security guard until he was shot on duty in 1990. Now he operates a food stall with his wife and three children in Mandaluyong in Metro Manila. The family earns about \$8 daily, which barely meets their needs. "We are scraping the bottom to get by."

■
Unlike many Asians, farmer Tong Chan of Dongkalungnur village in Lao PDR's Champassak Province says she wants her son to be a rice farmer when he grows up.

R. Cabrera

C. Detolph

Nine-year-old Ismail sells cigarettes, betel nut, and chewing gum outside Dhaka's Farmgate Market. He earns less than \$1 a day. Most of his money goes to buy rice for his family's two daily meals. He has never gone to school. Already grown-up, Ismail says he will do this for the rest of his life.

Wanrop Hirikul, a community leader in Bangkok's Klong Toey slum, came up with an innovative recycling idea where garbage—glass, plastic, and old newspapers—is collected by the slum dwellers and traded for eggs, rice, and other food. "I believe a cooperative project like this can help the urban poor improve their standard of living and self-esteem and the community's appearance—all at the same time," he says.

R. Cabrera

G. Hettel

Cambodian El Soey says she and her daughter are often hungry. They cannot afford to buy rice, so they pick wild vegetables, hunt for crabs and snails in the rice fields, and sometimes go to the Buddhist pagoda to get rice. She says she thinks about taking her daughter to an orphanage. "At least people would take care of her, and she'd have enough to eat."

Program Highlights

R. Kendrick

Irrigated rice is the keystone to Asia's food security, particularly for feeding urban consumers. About 80 million hectares of rice land are irrigated, producing about 75 percent of the world's rice. Yields vary from 3 to 9 tons per hectare and average 5 tons. Irrigated rice farmers generally use more purchased inputs than rainfed farmers.

Modern varieties for irrigated fields are short in duration and nitrogen responsive, and have multiple resistance to insect pests and diseases and some tolerance for problem soils. To surpass the yield potential of today's elite varieties, a new plant type is being developed and hybrid vigor exploited.

Perfecting the New Plant Type

In a year of exciting progress, numerous new plant type lines outperformed IR72, today's highest-yielding variety.

Thirty new plant type lines outyielded IR72 during the wet season, with the best seven averaging 6.6 tons per hectare compared with IR72's 5.0 tons. During the dry season, seven of the new plant type lines averaged 8.4 tons, topping IR72's 8.1 tons. The highest entry yielded 8.8 tons. "We feel confident that we have overcome the poor grain-filling obstacle we noticed in 1996," says Gurdev Khush, IRRI's principal plant breeder.

In an unexpected bonus, some of these promising lines have 50 percent more iron in their grain than ordinary rice. This can help combat malnutrition, especially among poor women and children (see p. 22).

Breeders are now concentrating on refining the new rice to build in resistance to brown planthopper and tungro, ensure its suitability for direct seeding, and make its grain appeal to the people who will eat it. Several hundred new crosses were made to develop lines with the long, slender grain preferred in tropical and subtropical Asia. The original lines have short, round

"IRRI has contributed greatly to our ability to produce more rice and we anxiously await the release of the new plant type, which promises our medium- and small-sized farmers a fighting chance to increase their productivity."

Justika S. Baharsjah
Minister of Social Affairs, Indonesia

Irrigated Rice

Rainfed Lowland Rice

Program Highlights

Rainfed lowland rice grows in banded fields that are flooded for at least part of the cropping season. Grown on 48 million hectares—mostly in South and Southeast Asia—rainfed lowland rice makes up about one-third of the world’s total rice area. Because of the variable and heterogeneous environment, where flooding, drought, and problem soils prevail, rice yields average only 2.3 tons per hectare.

Depending on rainfall to grow rice involves much risk: there may be too much water part of the year, and not enough at other times. Soil fertility is commonly low, and pests—such as weeds, brown spot, brown planthopper, gall midge, and blast—may also reduce yields. An enormous challenge exists to increase productivity while sustaining the resource base in the diverse targeted areas.

Understanding Farmers’ Management of Risks in Rice Farming

Eastern India is one of the world’s most densely populated regions—and one of the poorest. Across the harsh, extremely unpredictable landscape, rainfed lowland rice fields can produce a good crop one season—and then be flooded or scorched by drought the next.

When severe drought strikes, its impact usually lasts much longer than a cropping season. With no harvest, farmers are often forced to sell their draft animals, mortgage their land, and overexploit forest resources. The men sometimes migrate in search of work, leaving behind their families to make do, which often means reducing their meals of rice from three to two—and then to one—a day.

This chain of events sets off what IRRI agricultural economist Sushil Pandey calls an

“We know full well that growing rice in the areas with low suitability is expensive and may not be cost-effective at the moment. We have to pay a huge sum of money for the irrigation system, chemicals to improve the land, and research for new varieties of more resistant rice. Nevertheless, in the long run, with population growth and modern land use, we need more rice to feed the world, and we should find all means to improve rice yield.”

Her Royal Highness Princess Maha Chakri Sirindhorn
Thailand

R. Cabrera

Upland Rice

S. Appa Rao

Program Highlights

Nearly 100 million people depend on upland rice as their daily staple food.

Many of the world's poorest farmers live in the uplands of Asia, Africa, and Latin America, where farming systems are highly diverse.

More than 19 million hectares of upland rice are grown worldwide—around 63 percent of them in Asia. Upland rice areas vary in altitude from steeply sloping highlands of 2,500 meters to gently sloping areas only a few meters above sea level. The defining feature is not altitude but that upland rice grows on well-drained soils without standing water—just like other dryland crops, such as maize and wheat.

Enhancing upland rice productivity provides an entry point to reducing the interrelated problems of subsistence agriculture—low productivity, weed infestations, and soil erosion—that create severe poverty in the fragile uplands.

Farmers' Tastes Getting Attention

The higher yields of improved varieties are important. But if upland farmers don't like the taste of the rice they grow, chances are they'll stick with their traditional low-yielding but good-tasting varieties. And that's why researchers are paying attention to farmers' tastes.

For the past two years, farmers in eastern India, in Korahar, Hazaribag district (Bihar), and in Sariyawan, Faizabad district (Uttar Pradesh), have been giving their opinions on what they like and don't like in the higher-yielding varieties they're helping to develop through farmer participatory plant breeding. This includes the way their rice should look after cooking and how it should taste.

"To produce and supply enough food and the daily necessities for the increasing human population will be a longstanding lofty duty of the world science community."

Song Jian
Vice Chairman, Chinese People's Political Consultative Conference, and President, Chinese Academy of Engineering Sciences

Flood-Prone Rice

“The Green Revolution has won a temporary success in humanity’s war against hunger and deprivation. If fully implemented, the revolution can provide sufficient food for sustenance during the next three decades. But the frightening power of human reproduction must also be curbed; otherwise the success of the Green Revolution will be ephemeral only.”

Norman Borlaug
Nobel Peace Prize Laureate

Program Highlights

About 13 million hectares of rice land, mainly in South and Southeast Asia, experience uncontrolled flooding. Rice yields are low—often less than 1 ton per hectare—and extremely variable because of problem soils and unpredictable combinations of drought and flood.

Three major types of flood-prone rice exist: deepwater, which tolerates water depths of 50-100 centimeters; floating, which can be found in water up to 400 centimeters deep; and tidal wetland, which can survive short periods of submergence, often in salty water.

Increasing the annual rice harvest in these areas is a critical social and economic challenge. Larger rice yields will improve the profitability of farming systems and the quality of life for millions of extremely poor people who must survive in these flood-prone areas.

Consortium for Improving Flood-Prone Systems

Cropping intensity needs to be increased and farming systems diversified in the fragile flood-prone ecosystem of South and Southeast Asia to improve the livelihood of millions of extremely poor people living in these places.

“We cannot live on rice alone,” said one woman in India’s Bihar State. “We need to be able to grow other food crops or be able to buy food from the money we earn from our farms.”

To evaluate and adapt promising technologies through farmer participatory research, IRRI helped to establish the Flood-Prone Rice Research Consortium in early 1999. Scientists from Bangladesh, India, Thailand, Sri Lanka, and Vietnam are joining forces to solve some of the extremely complex problems in these densely populated,

R. Cabrera

Cross-Ecosystems Research

“It is vital that we undertake the necessary research, improve our knowledge, and ensure that poor people gain access to both that knowledge and technologies. The world has agreed to poverty eradication targets that involve 1 billion people being lifted out of poverty within 20 years. To achieve this target, the income levels of the rural poor will have to improve; relevant research that is well disseminated is key to this aim.”

Rt. Honorable Clare Short, MP
Secretary of State for International
Development, United Kingdom

Program Highlights

New Links for Communicating with Farmers

With future gains in rice production increasingly coming from knowledge-intensive technologies, scientists are facing a new challenge. “Farmers can go to a shop and buy fertilizer and seed,” says Mark Bell, head of IRRI’s Agricultural Engineering Division. “But where do they go to get knowledge?”

Reaching the huge number of subsistence farmers across Asia’s rice lands is not easy. “If we’re going to improve farmers’ livelihoods, they need knowledge about the options available to them,” says Dr. Bell. “We need a framework for identifying constraints and reasonable technologies for farmers to use, and then getting information about the options to them.”

So new agents of change—nongovernment organizations (NGOs) and the private sector—are being enlisted to serve alongside government organizations on the frontline of the technology transfer process. Some large NGOs provide a range of services to the rural poor, including training, information, micro-credit, and health care. Some, such as the Bangladesh Rural Advancement Committee, have vast networks of staff members who work closely with farmers.

Initial projects are in Thailand (improved water management through land-leveling and improved weed management) and Bangladesh (a new cropping system). These efforts link NGOs, the private sector, national research and extension organizations, and IRRI (see p. 35). The information provided and the technologies demonstrated were determined by the farmers’ own needs and interests. Brochures in local languages, farmer discussion groups, and on-farm development and demonstrations of technologies in key villages are the elements of the extension package.

“We see these on-farm demonstrations as a vehicle for technology modification, further communication, and research feedback,” explains Len Wade, agronomist and interim leader of IRRI’s rainfed lowland rice research program. How these technologies influence socioeconomic status and gender relations is also being studied.

To get information to the intermediaries who are working with the farmers, researchers are developing a decision-support system that transforms the most important elements of demonstrations and puts them in an electronic format.

Strengthening Partnerships

R. Cabrera

“Perhaps one of the greatest challenges will be to grow rice in a way that smallholder producers, especially on marginal lands, are adequately compensated, while being able to sell rice at a price that is affordable to low-income consumers. Minimizing production costs is the only way these twin objectives can be achieved.”

Siene Saphangthong
Minister of Agriculture, Lao PDR

Program Highlights

Fields of Hope: Helping Lowland Farmers in Lao PDR

In the Lao People's Democratic Republic, rice seems to be everywhere: rice fields cover 645,000 hectares, people eat rice two or three times a day, and rice motifs are woven into silk. Even the phrase for eating rice is synonymous with eating food.

Although eight out of every 10 Lao are rice farmers, rice farming is not a lucrative occupation. Farmers' incomes are less than \$100 a year, while the national average was \$385 in 1996. Rice farming is also risky, with most farmers growing only one crop a year. Because the crop depends on rainfall, too much water or too little water can mean a poor harvest—and hunger. Yields range from 2 to 2.5 tons per hectare, but less than 1 ton is common.

Lao PDR, however, is in the midst of a renaissance in rice production. An ambitious national policy aims to increase production to 2.1 million tons by 2000 from the 1.7 million tons of rice produced in 1997, through a combination of improved yields and increased area under rice cultivation in the rainfed lowland and irrigated environments. Rice production is being discouraged in the fragile uplands to limit further environmental degradation. Thanks to rice research, the country is well on its way to meeting these goals.

“The major challenge is getting smallholder producers to adopt technologies to achieve the yield and production targets,” says Lao Minister of Agriculture Siene Saphangthong.

Building and Sustaining Research

In 1990, only six people were in the National Rice Research Program. Now, more than 120 coordinators, scientists, and technicians in all 16 of the country's provinces and Vientiane Municipality are involved in a research network.

The efforts of the Lao-IRRI Research and Training Project, which is helping the country strengthen its rice research capacity and effectiveness, have had a lot to do with these achievements. With financial support from the Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation (SDC), the project has also been building and upgrading infrastructure, including the National Agricultural Research Center and six research stations. “To ensure sustainability, IRRI has been trying

Finance and Administration

(Clockwise) John D. Rockefeller, Robert Chandler, Henry Beachell (kneeling), unidentified

“Agricultural development remains vital to reducing poverty and eliminating hunger. The challenges will become even greater in the years ahead as environmental circumstances change and global population steadily increases. No organization has been more instrumental in helping provide opportunities to small farmers in Asia than IRRI.”

Thomas C. Hubbard
United States Ambassador to the Philippines

Program Highlights

Leadership Changes

The IRRI senior management team underwent a major transition during 1998 and early 1999. Dr. Ronald P. Cantrell became the new IRRI director general in September 1998. A new director for finance, Mr. Gordon MacNeil, began his duties in July 1998, and Dr. William Padolina became the director for external relations in January 1999.

Long-serving deputy director general for research Dr. Kenneth Fischer finished his term in April 1999, and Ms. Paulette Coburn, director for administration and human resources, resigned. ■

National Staff Job Evaluation Completed

IRRI completed a major wage and salary restructuring exercise in 1998 for its national staff. With the assistance of an outside consulting firm and an employee-led task force, all positions institute-wide were rated on criteria that measured responsibility. Positions were then placed in various job grades.

Salaries were increased to be commensurate with the top quartile of the Philippine market for similar position responsibilities. ■

More Awards for Gurdev Khush

IRRI's principal plant breeder and World Food Prize laureate, Gurdev S. Khush, received the Rank Prize for Nutrition in December 1998. The prize was presented by Lord Deering of the Royal Society of Medicine in London.

Additionally, he was named one of 50 outstanding Asians by *Business Magazine*, and received a medal from the Government of Vietnam for his contribution “to the cause of agriculture and rural development of Vietnam.” He was named honorary professor of Shenyang Agricultural University in China, and received a Doctor of Science (Honoris Causa) degree from De Montfort University, Leicester, United Kingdom.

Dr. Khush joined IRRI in 1967 after earning his PhD in genetics at the University of California at Davis. He has been the Institute's principal plant breeder for many years, as well as head of the Plant Breeding, Genetics, and Biochemistry Division. He is featured on the Riceworld web site at <http://www.riceworld.org/drkopen.html>. ■

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“One-sixth of the human family still lives in abject poverty, environmental degradation continues apace, and, over the next quarter century, the world must feed another 90 million people each year. Those who care about the fate and future of the human family must form a coalition if the challenges of the 21st century are to be overcome.”

Ismail Serageldin
Chairman, CGIAR

CGIAR Centers

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|----------------|---|--------------|--|
| CIAT | Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical
Cali, Colombia | IFPRI | International Food Policy Research Institute
Washington, D.C., United States |
| CIFOR | Center for International Forestry Research
Bogor, Indonesia | IITA | International Institute of Tropical Agriculture
Ibadan, Nigeria |
| CIMMYT | Centro Internacional de Mejoramiento de Maíz y Trigo
Mexico, D.F., Mexico | ILRI | International Livestock Research Institute
Nairobi, Kenya |
| CIP | Centro Internacional de la Papa
Lima, Peru | IPGRI | International Plant Genetic Resources Institute
Rome, Italy |
| ICARDA | International Center for Agricultural Research in the Dry Areas
Aleppo, Syrian Arab Republic | IRRI | International Rice Research Institute
Los Baños, Laguna, Philippines |
| ICLARM | International Center for Living Aquatic Resources Management
Manila, Philippines | ISNAR | International Service for National Agricultural Research
The Hague, The Netherlands |
| ICRAF | International Centre for Research in Agroforestry
Nairobi, Kenya | IWMI | International Water Management Institute
Colombo, Sri Lanka |
| ICRISAT | International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics
Patancheru, India | WARDA | West Africa Rice Development Association
Bouaké, Côte d'Ivoire |

“Hunger remains one of the most critical concerns facing developing countries in Asia. To eliminate hunger, it is imperative that we continue to support and encourage sustainable growth in food production. Furthermore, conscious efforts should be made to ensure equitable access to food for the poor, particularly women, children, and indigenous people.”

Tadao Chino
President, Asian Development Bank